

USED IN PRIMARY CLASSES METHODS

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Abstract. *In this method, there are different types used in primary classes information about methods is provided.*

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Pedagogical novelty - previously unknown in the educational process in pedagogical activity the theory and practice of education and upbringing by introducing changes is a means of enrichment and its development. Indeed, modern pedagogy technologies increase the productivity of the educational process, students are independent forms the thinking process, students' passion and interest in knowledge increases, solid assimilation of knowledge, free use of it in practice forms skills and competencies. The child's thinking is now formed the skills of the teacher in the upcoming primary classes, his pedagogy ability to skillfully apply technologies to the educational process, the novelty of education it is very possible to search for methods and methods, to be able to creatively use pedagogical experiences is important. Therefore, introducing pedagogical innovations into the educational process, A the use of pedagogical technologies in education, from various innovative methods and methods use, the constant search for increasing the effectiveness of education today became a necessity. It is known that today in the course of the lesson "Brainstorming", "Crossword", "Sinkway", "Museum", "Case study", "Insert", "Venn diagram" and "BBB" technologies are used in the organization of the educational process. This methodology serves to ensure the effectiveness and quality of the teaching process We recommend several more innovative methods. "Find video" method Nowadays, various media (computer, television, radio, copier, slide, video and audio tape recorders).special attention is paid to the organization of the educational process. In front of teachers appropriate and purposeful use of various media in the educational process has a task.

When using the video puzzle method, the following actions are performed:

- help to bring to the students' attention the essence of the topic being studied several videos are shown without commentary;
- students explain what process is shown in each picture;
- record the nature of the processes in their notebooks;
- answer the questions asked by the teacher.

Based on this method, a video on the topic is shown through a computer. Students express their opinions about the topic of the video and the topic expressed in it. The "Advertising" method is mainly effective in elementary school reading classes shows. The stages of the teaching process of this method are: asking about the topic and can be used to reinforce a new topic. A teacher in this process gives students handouts according to the essence of the topic, in them "Advertise!" the main rule is that the combination is written.

Pupils are specific to the topic given in the handouts, to the person or object in it by advertising through qualities, actions, excerpts from the work, role-playing instructions they will

have to give. As well as extracurricular reading lessons from this method also in recommending poems, fairy tales, stories and other small works can be used. In this case, a student or group of students, to other students Recommends poems, fairy tales, stories and other short works for reading, different forms of advertising are used in the recommendation process. "Advertisement" The advantage of the method can be seen in the following:

- students' speech becomes more fluent, they can speak in front of the team, express their thoughts freely communication skills are formed;

- a meaningful organization of the lesson process is achieved, students attend the lesson interests increase, respect for books and works of art is formed in them his desire to study increases;

- students' outlook will expand, a healthy competitive environment will emerge, respect other people's opinions, listen carefully to them, concentrate and thinking skills are formed.

"Rainbow polish" method should be used for primary classes is appropriate. This method is also used in mother tongue, mathematics and reading classes can be used. For example: classifying words into categories in native language classes words like doll, car, laughed, cried, yellow, big, small, nine categorization and noun grouping words in blue line placement, the task of placing the words of the adjective group on the air color line is given. This is during the division of numbers into unit units in mathematics class method can be used. That is, the first color of the rainbow is a one-digit number if we get, the color in the second row can be an example of a two-digit number.

Through the "Rainbow Polish" method, children acquire the following knowledge, skills, and abilities adjectives are formed:

- the student remembers the category of words by colors;
- the student develops ideas about natural phenomena, in which the environment and love for nature and the skills to preserve it are formed;
- students' worldview and scope of imagination expands, concentration, thinking, intelligence and resourcefulness skills develop.

"Fifth (sixth, seventh ...) plus" method

This method allows students to acquire logical thinking skills is of particular importance. When using it, the following actions are performed:

- Concepts that serve to reveal the essence of the subject being studied system formation;
- four (five, six, ...) related to the topic from the resulting system and related to achieve the occurrence of one non-existent concept;

- to help students identify a concept that is not related to the topic and remove it from the system assigning the task of issuing;

- encourage students to interpret the essence of their actions (strengthening the topic with the aim of asking the students to comment on the concepts stored in the system it is necessary to demand that they pass and justify the logical connection between them).

This method is based on the topic (or section, chapter) being studied by students Analytical reasoning, as well as express the most important basic concepts requires receiving.

In conclusion, we can say that information communication system primary education teacher in a highly developing process deep knowledge of technique and technology, ability to analyze and create innovation

It is very important to be educated and skilled at the level. To organize a lesson for this in the process of choosing methods that are understandable, easy and interesting for all students and

can apply, use visual aids, newly produced apply technical tools, encourage learners to work creatively and independently, it is desirable to use pedagogical technologies correctly and efficiently.

It is aimed at increasing students' vocabulary and developing their speech

Riddles are important in improving the effectiveness of mother tongue lessons have Nowadays, new pedagogical technologies in the educational process the application of interactive methods to the educational process is increasing day by day is going Interactive methods help students to work, concentrate, invites them to work independently, to think, to search, to their lessons interest increases, participation in the lesson becomes more active, and the efficiency of the lesson increases serves.

Ways to apply active methods of education, creative thinkers, education of morally perfect individuals to today's students is putting a serious responsibility. Accordingly, we are responsible we tried to find a solution to the task. In primary grades interesting games-tasks to increase student activity, from riddles and modern pedagogical technologies (from computers, non-traditional teaching methods, interactive methods) productive use is desirable.

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